

GIPERBOLIK TIPDAGI TENGLAMA UCHUN CHEGARAVIY MASALALAR HAQIDA

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada beshburchakli sohada giperbolik tipdagi tenglama uchun ikkita chegaraviy masalalar bayon qilingan va bir qiymatli yechilishi isbotlangan.

Аннотация. В этой статье поставлены две краевые задачи для уравнения гиперболического типа в пятиугольной области и доказано однозначное решение.

Annotation. In this article, two boundary value problems for a hyperbolic type equation in a pentagonal domain are stated and a one-value solution is proved.

Kalit so'zlar: Giperbolik tipdagi tenglama; Gursa masalasi; Koshi masalasi; Dalamber formulasi.

Ключевые слова: Уравнение гиперболического типа; проблема Гурсы; вопрос Коши; формула Даламбера.

Key words: Hyperbolic type equation; Gursa issue; Cauchy issue; Dalamber formula.

Kirish.Masalaning qo'yilishi. Ma'lumki giperbolik tipdagi tenglamalar ko'plab to'lqin tarqalish jarayonlarini ifodalagani uchun amaliy masalalar ko'p uchraydi [1]. Masalan ovoz to'lqinlari biror to'siqqa urilishi natijasida boshqa to'lqin bo'ylab yo'naladi. Bunday jarayonlardan tenglama giperbolik tipga tegishli ekanligini saqlaydi ammo tenglamaning ko'rinishi o'zgarishi mumkin. Shu sababdan biz ushbu ishda giperbolik tipdagi tenglama uchun ikkita chegaraviy masalani o'rganamiz.

Ω bilan Oxy tekisligining $x + y = 0$, $x - y = 1$, $x = 0$, $x = 1$, $y = a$ to'g'ri chiziqlar bilan chegaralangan chekli soha ($0 \leq x \leq 1$, $-1/2 < y < a$) ni belgilaylik, bu yerda $a = const > 0$.

Ushbu $\Omega_1 = \Omega \cap (y > 0)$, $\Omega_2 = \Omega \cap (y < 0)$, $AE = \{(x, a) : 0 < x < 1\}$,
 $OA = \{(0, y) : 0 < y < a\}$, $OB = \{(x, 0) : 0 < x < 1\}$, $OM = \{(x, y) : y = -x, 0 < x < 1/2\}$,
 $BM = \{(x, y) : y = x - 1, (1/2) < x < 1\}$ belgishlarni kiritaylik.

Ω sohada

$$0 = \begin{cases} u_{xy} + \lambda^2 u(x, y); & y > 0 \\ u_{xx} - u_{yy} & ; \quad y < 0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

tenglamani qaraylik. Bu tenglama Ω_1 sohada giperbolik tipga tegishli telegraf tenglamasi bo'ladi.

Ω_2 sohada esa tor tebranish tenglamasi bo'ladi. Shuning uchun (1) tenglama Ω sohada giperbolik tipdagi tenglama bo'ladi. Bu tenglamaning xarakteristikalari Ω_1 va Ω_2 sohalarda mos ravishda $x = 1$, $y = a$ va $x \pm y = C$ chiziqlardan iborat bo'lib, OB kesma ham xarakteristika bo'ladi.

(1) tenglama uchun Ω sohada quyidagi masalani o'rganamiz:

T masala. Shunday funksiya topilsinki, u Ω_1 va Ω_2 sohalarda (1) tenglamani, OB kesmada

$$u(x, +0) = u(x, -0), \quad 0 \leq x \leq 1; \quad u_y(x, +0) = u_y(x, -0), \quad 0 < x < 1 \quad (2)$$

ulash shartlarini va quyidagi chegaraviy shartlarni qanoatlantirsin:

$$u(0, y) = \varphi(y), \quad 0 \leq y < a \quad (3)$$

$$u(x, y) \Big|_{OM} = u(x, -x) = \psi(x), \quad 0 \leq x \leq 1/2 \quad (4)$$

bu yerda $\varphi(y)$, $\psi(x)$ – berilgan funksiyalar bo‘lib, $\varphi(0) = \psi(0)$ kelishuv sharti bajariladi.

Masalaning bir qiymatli yechilishini isbotlaymiz. Faraz qilaylik, $u(x, y)$ -qo‘yilgan masalaning yechimi bo‘lsin. Masala shartlariga asoslanib, quyidagi belgilashlarni va farazlarni qabul qilaylik:

$$u(x, 0) = \tau(x), \quad 0 \leq x \leq 1; \quad \tau(x) \in C[0,1] \cap C^2(0,1), \quad (5)$$

$$u_y(x, 0) = \nu(x), \quad 0 < x < 1; \quad \nu(x) \in C^1(0,1) \cap L[0,1]. \quad (6)$$

U holda $u(x, y)$ funksiya Ω_2 sohada (1) tenglama uchun (5), (6) boshlang‘ich shartlar bilan qo‘yilgan Koshi masalasining yechimi

$$u(x, y) = \frac{\tau(x-y) + \tau(x+y)}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \int_{x-y}^{x+y} \nu(\xi) d\xi \quad (7)$$

ko‘rinishda bo‘ladi [2]. Bu (7) formulani (4) chegaraviy shartga bo‘ysundirsak

$$u(x, y) \Big|_{OM} = u(x, -x) = \frac{1}{2} [\tau(0) + \tau(2x)] + \frac{1}{2} \int_{2x}^0 2\nu(\xi) d\xi = \psi(x), \quad 0 \leq x \leq 1/2,$$

ya’ni

$$\tau(0) + \tau(2x) + \int_{2x}^0 2\nu(\xi) d\xi = 2\psi(x), \quad 0 \leq x \leq 1/2$$

tenglik kelib chiqadi. Bu tenglikda $2x = z \in [0,1]$ belgilash kiritib, so‘ngra z o‘zgaruvchi bo‘yicha hosila olsak, $\tau(x)$ va $\nu(x)$ noma’lum funksiyalar orasidagi Ω_2 sohada olingan asosiy funksional munosabatga ega bo‘lamiz:

$$\tau'(z) - \nu(z) = \psi'(z/2), \quad 0 < z < 1. \quad (8)$$

$u(x, y) \in C(\bar{\Omega})$ va $u_y(x, y) \in C(\Omega)$ ekanligini e’tiborga olib, (1) tenglamada (2) ulash shartlarini, (3) chegaraviy shartni va (5), (6) belgilashlarni hisobga olsak munosabat kelib chiqadi.

$$\tau(0) = \varphi(0) = \psi(0) \quad (9)$$

Agar (8), (9) tengliklardan foydalanib, $\tau(x) \in C[0,1] \cap C^2(0,1)$ va $\nu(x) \in C^1(0,1) \cap L[0,1]$ noma’lum funksiyalar bir qiymatli topilsa, u holda qo‘yilgan masalaning yechimi Ω_2 sohada (7) formula bilan, Ω_1 sohada esa formula bilan topiladi [3]:

$$u(x, y) = \varphi(y) + \tau(x) - \varphi(0) \lambda^2 J_0 \left[2\lambda \sqrt{(y-\eta)x} \right] - \lambda^2 x \int_0^y \varphi(\eta) J_1 \left[2\lambda \sqrt{(y-\eta)x} \right] -$$

$$-\lambda^2 y \int_0^x \tau(\xi) J_1 \left[2\lambda \sqrt{(x-\xi)y} \right], \quad (10)$$

bu yerda $J_\gamma(x) - \gamma$ tartibli birinchi tur Bessel funksiyasi.

(10) formulani (6) shartga bo'ysundiramiz hamda $\tau(x)$ va $\nu(x)$ noma'lum funksiyalar orasidagi Ω_1 sohada olingan asosiy funksional munosabatga ega bo'lamiz:

$$\varphi'(0) - \lambda^2 \int_0^x \tau(\xi) d\xi = \nu(x) \quad (11)$$

(8) va (11) dan foydalanib,

$$\tau'(x) + \lambda^2 \int_0^x \tau(\xi) d\xi = \psi'(x/2) + \varphi'(0),$$

tenglamani hosil qilamiz. Bu tenglamadani $[0, x]$ bo'yicha integrallaymiz (9) dan foydalanib, quyidagi integral tenglamani hosil qilamiz:

$$\tau(x) + \lambda^2 \int_0^x (x-\xi) \tau(\xi) d\xi = 2\psi(x/2) - 2\psi(0) + \varphi'(0)x + \varphi(0)$$

Bu integral tenglamani ketma-ket yaqinlashishlar usuli yordamida yechamiz. Ko'rsatish qiyin emaski, $K(x, \xi) = (x - \xi)$ yadroning rezolventasi

$$R(x, \xi; \lambda) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^n \lambda^{2n} (x-\xi)^{2n+1}}{(2n+1)!} = \frac{1}{\lambda} \sin[\lambda(x-\xi)]$$

ko'rinshda bo'ladi.

Bu rezolventa orqali $\tau(x)$ funksiyani quyidagicha topamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} \tau(x) = & 2\psi(x/2) - 2\psi(0)\cos \lambda x + \varphi(0)\cos \lambda x + \\ & + \frac{1}{\lambda} \varphi'(0)\sin \lambda x - 2\lambda \int_0^x \sin[\lambda(x-\xi)] \cdot \psi(\xi/2) d\xi. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

(12) tenglikdan hosila olib, uni (8) ga qo'yib, $\nu(x)$ funksiyani quyidagi ko'rinshda topamiz:

$$\nu(x) = \lambda \varphi(0)\sin \lambda x + \varphi'(0)\cos \lambda x - 2\lambda^2 \int_0^x \cos[\lambda(x-\xi)] \cdot \psi(\xi/2) d\xi.$$

Agar $\psi(x) \in C[0, 1/2] \cap C^2(0, 1/2)$, $\varphi(x) \in C^1[0, 1]$, deb faraz qilsak, topilgan $\tau(x)$ funksiya $C[0, 1] \cap C^2(0, 1)$ sinfga, $\nu(x)$ funksiya esa $C^1(0, 1) \cap L[0, 1]$ sinfga tegishli bo'ladi. Topilgan $\tau(x)$ va $\nu(x)$ funksiyalarni (8) va (10) formulalarga qo'yib, T masalaning yechimini Ω_1 va Ω_2 sohalarda topamiz.

O'rganilgan masala yechimining yagonaligi (1) tenglamaning $y > 0$ qismi uchun (3), (4) Gursa masalasi yechimining, $y < 0$ qismi uchun (5), (6) Koshi masalasi yechimining yagonaligidan kelib chiqadi.

Endi Ω sohada (1) tenglama uchun quyidagi nolokal masalani tadqiq etamiz.

BS masala. T masalaning barcha shartlarini qanoatlantirib, (4) shartni o'rniga

$$u(x/2, -x/2) + u(x, 0) = \beta(x), \quad x \in [0, 1] \quad (14)$$

nolokal shartni qanoatlantirsin, bu yerda $\varphi(y), \beta(x)$ - berilgan funksiyalar bo'lib, $2\varphi(0) = \beta(0)$ kelishuv sharti bajariladi. Agar biz $\tau(x)$ va $\nu(x)$ funksiyalarni bir qiymatli topa olsak, Ω_1 sohada masalaning (2), (3) shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi yechimi T masalaniki kabi (10) formula bilan topiladi.

Ω_2 soha uchun BS masalaning $u(x, y)$ yechimini hozircha noma'lum bo'lgan $\tau(x)$ va $\nu(x)$ funksiyalar orqali bir qiymatli topamiz.

(7) ni (14) shartga bo'ysundirib

$$\frac{\tau(0) + \tau(x)}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \int_0^x \nu(z) dz + \tau(x) = \beta(x) \quad (15)$$

tenglamani hosil qilamiz. (11) dagi $\nu(x)$ funksiya (15) ga qo'yib, $\tau(x)$ funksiyaga nisbatan

$$\tau(x) = \varphi(0) - 2\beta(x) - x\varphi'(0) + \lambda^2 \int_0^x (x - \xi) \tau(\xi) d\xi$$

Bu integral tenglamani ketma-ket yaqinlashishlar usuli yordamida yechamiz. Ko'rsatish qiyin emaski, $K(x, \xi) = (x - \xi)$ yadroning rezolventasi

$$R(x, \xi; \lambda) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\lambda}} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{[\sqrt{\lambda}(x - \xi)]^{2k+1}}{(2k+1)!} = \frac{sh[\sqrt{\lambda}(x - \xi)]}{\sqrt{\lambda}}$$

ko'rinishida bo'ladi va biz bu rezolventa yordamida $\tau(x)$ ni topishimiz mumkin bo'ladi:

$$\begin{aligned} \tau(x) = & \varphi(0) - 2\beta(x) - x\varphi'(0) - \lambda\varphi(0) + \\ & + \lambda\varphi(0)ch(\sqrt{\lambda}x) + \lambda\varphi'(0)x - \lambda\varphi'(0)sh(\sqrt{\lambda}x) - \\ & - 2\lambda\sqrt{\lambda} \int_0^x sh[\sqrt{\lambda}(x - \xi)]\beta(\xi) d\xi \end{aligned}$$

(11) ga asosan, $\nu(x)$ ni quyidagicha topamiz;

$$\begin{aligned} \nu(x) = & \varphi'(0) - \lambda^2\varphi(0)x + \frac{1}{2}\lambda^2\varphi'(0)x^2 + \lambda^3\varphi(0)x - \lambda^2\sqrt{\lambda}\varphi(0)sh(\sqrt{\lambda}x) - \\ & - \frac{1}{2}\lambda^3\varphi'(0)x^2 + \lambda^2\sqrt{\lambda}\varphi'(0)ch(\sqrt{\lambda}x) - \\ & - \lambda^2\sqrt{\lambda}\varphi'(0) - 2\lambda^2 \int_0^x \beta(\xi) d\xi + 2\lambda^3 \int_0^x \beta(\xi) d\xi + \\ & + 2\lambda^3 \int_0^x \beta(\xi)ch[\sqrt{\lambda}(x - \xi)] d\xi. \end{aligned}$$

Agar $\beta(x) \in C[0, 1] \cap C^2(0, 1), \varphi(x) \in C^1[0, 1]$ deb faraz qilsak, $\tau(x)$ ham $C[0, 1] \cap C^2(0, 1)$ sinfga, $\nu(x)$ esa $C^1(0, 1) \cap L(0, 1)$ sinfga tegishli bo'ladi. Topilgan $\tau(x)$ va

$\nu(x)$ funksiyalarni (8) va (10) formulalarga qo'yib, BS masalaning yechimini Ω_1 va Ω_2 sohalarda topamiz.

O'rganilgan masala yechimining yagonaligi, $\tau(x)$ va $\nu(x)$ funksiyalarning bir qiymatli topilganidan kelib chiqadi.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR

1. Тихонов А. Н., Самарский А. А. Уравнения математической физики.-М.:Наука, 1966.-724 с.
2. Салоҳитдинов М. С. Математик физика тенгламалари-Тошкент: Ўзбекистон, 200.-448с.
3. Уринов А. К. Телеграф тенгламаси учун чегаравий масалалар.-Ташкент: Университет, 1996.-48с.